

Review of The Optimization Algorithms for Remanufacturing Disassembly Line

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Abstract—The disassembly line of remanufacturing has significance economic and social value for dealing with the massive increasing number of disposal products. As the typical multi-objective optimization (MOO) problem, disassembly line balancing problem (DLBP) has the characteristic of high computational complexity (NP-hard). There has no summarize of MOO algorithms for the remanufacturing DLBP. Therefore, this paper main reviewed three main categories of the optimization algorithms for remanufacturing DLBP and comparing the advantages and disadvantages of various algorithms. Additionally, identify the challenges and future research directions of remanufacturing DLBP.

Keywords- Remanufacturing; Disassembly sequence planning; Disassembly line balancing; Applicable algorithms; DLBP research trends

I. INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing industry has made great contributions to the rapid development of society and economy. With the rapid development of modern smart manufacturing, the disposal speed of products has also accelerated, resulting in great increase about the number of disposal products. The increase number of disposal products will aggravate the shortage of existing resources and environmental pollution, which seriously affecting the sustainable development [1].

In order to extend the life cycle of products and realize the full use of resources, the concept of remanufacturing is proposed [2]. The remanufacturing process takes the end of life (EOL) disposal products as the object, mainly through disassembly, cleaning/inspection, sorting, re-processing and re-assembly processes so that the performance and quality can achieve the level of the origin products [3]. The entire life cycle of process of products as shown in Figure 1. Remanufacturing can effectively reduce costs and save energy and promoting sustainable development [4].

Disassembly process is one of the most important part of the remanufacturing process. The concept of end-of-life (EOL) products disassembly first proposed by Gupta [5], and it refers to the process of systematically separating valuable parts from hazardous parts. Disassembly process can obtain complete components, maximize the use of resources, and minimize the harm to the environment during processing.

Early disassembly of disposal products was mainly carried out on independent disassembly cell or single workstations [6]. In order to find a reasonable disassembly

path, [7] first proposed the sequence planning problem of product disassembly process. With the rapid increase in the number of disposal products, for improving the disassembly efficiency, the disassembly line composed of multiple workstations has become the best choice for massive disassembly of disposal products. The comparison of advantages and disadvantages between disassembly cell, single workstation and disassembly line as shown in table 1. However, the disassembly line is prone to uneven distribution of tasks among various workstations, which affects the efficiency and increases the costs of disassembly line. For solving this problem, [8] proposed the disassembly line balancing problem (DLBP) and detailed analyze the various challenges faced by the problem. The design and installation of the disassembly line requires long-term decision-making and large amount of investment.

Figure 1. The process of remanufacturing

TABLE I. COMPARE OF DISASSEMBLY TYPE

Disassembly Type	Advantages	Disadvantages	Product Type
Disassembly cell	Highly flexible	Low efficiency High costs	Single
Single workstation	Highly flexible Medium costs	Low efficiency High setup times	Single
Disassembly line	High efficiency Automation	Less flexible High complexity	Multiple types

The key technology of DLBP is how to allocate disassembly tasks to each disassembly workstation for ensuring the disassembly line can operate efficiently. Research shows that the DLBP is NP-hard problem [9]. The problem of disassembly line balance includes the following three steps: selecting the type of disassembly line, determine product category, and developing the appropriate method for disassembly line balance. The first step of disassembly sequence planning is to select the appropriate disassembly mode. Then, the disassembly sequencing methods are used to describe the disassembly constraint relationship of disposal products to ensure the generated disassembly sequence is one of the feasible solutions. Finally, the optimization algorithms are proposed to find

the optimal disassembly sequence from many feasible solutions.

The research state of the art on DLBP was reviewed in this study, from the proposed optimization algorithms. The research challenges and trends were also discussed in this research area. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: the methods and algorithms proposed for DLBP are reviewed in section II. The research challenges and future trends are discussed in section III. And the last section is the remarks and conclusion.

II. THE REVIEW OF ALGORITHMS FOR REMANUFACTURING DISASSEMBLY LINE

Since the DLBP can be abstracted into the multi-objective optimization mathematical model, many researchers have adopted a variety of algorithms for different types of DLBP, which can be summarized into three main categories: The first category is the exact algorithm, which is traditional mathematical programming methods, searching for the most accurate and optimal solution of the target functions. The second type is heuristic algorithm or traditional heuristic algorithm, which formulate corresponding heuristic rules according to different problems, then assign weights to each task based on the designed rules, and finally select and allocate the task weight, for achieving the better solution to the target functions. The third category is the meta-heuristic algorithm, also known as swarm intelligence algorithm or modern biological algorithm, which simulates the principles of biological population foraging and evolution, finding the most approximate optimal solution of the target functions. The general classification of DLBP solving algorithm is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The classification of DLBP algorithm

A. Exact algorithm

The exact algorithms based on the traditional mathematical programming methods for solving remanufacturing DLBP, mainly including mixed integer linear programming (MILP), mixed integer nonlinear programming (MINLP), stochastic programming (SP), dynamic programming (DP), and fuzzy programming (FP) as shown in Figure 3. These exact algorithms can find the exact optimal solution, which are based on the certain single optimization objective and under given conditions.

The MILP model is the mutation of the basis of the linear programming (LP) model some decision integer variables. Bentaha *et al.* assumed the disassembly time as the random variable with a known probability distribution and applied the AND/OR diagram to indicate the disassembly sequence, for achieving the most optimal allocation of tasks on the disassembly line and realizing the maximize profit of disassembly process [10]. Shabanpour and Colledani proposed a mathematical optimization model for achieving the maximum profit under uncertain task

times [11]. Edis *et al.* developed a generic MILP model for solving the single model DLBP, considered the demand quantities, direction changes and analyzed through the cases studies [12]. Mete *et al.* addressed a novel MILP model, considering the change cycle time of disassembly because of the variation of supply for rebalancing the disassembly lines and decreasing the total cost [13]. Slaha *et al.* proposed a new MILP model for solving the capacitated disassembly scheduling problem focus on the single product type, multi-layer and multi-period problem, achieving maximizing the total profit [14].

Figure 3. The classification of exact algorithm

The MINLP model is another type of LP model, in which, the decision variables include integer and continuous variables. Kannan integrated a MINLP model into reverse supply chain logistics network from the perspective of the third party, for retrieving the maximum value [15]. Liu and Zhang proposed a MINLP for the multi-period dis-assembly scheduling problem under random yields and demands, improving the efficiency of the algorithm [16]. Liu *et al.* proposed a MINLP for balancing the workload of disassembly line based the entropy [17]. Yolmeh and Saif developed a MINLP model integrate the disassembly line balancing decisions into the network design of the closed-loop supply chain [18].

SP is an extension of linear programming, which is suitable for solving the uncertain decision-making problems. The central problem of SP is to select parameters to maximize the mathematical expectation of profit or minimize the mathematical expectation of cost. The stochastic programming can effectively solve the problem of minimum workstations and maximum profitability. Altekin *et al.* also programmed the profit-oriented disassembly line with stochastic task time, and considered the relevant cost remedial measures and methods [19]. He *et al.* studied the disassembly line balancing problem of green directional dual objectives with SP time, considering the design cost of the disassembly production line and the total emissions [20]. Liu *et al.* also based the stochastic task processing times, considering the DLBP under partial uncertain knowledge for improving the robust of disassembly system [21].

DP is the process of solving the optimization process of decision-making, and it is effective for solving multi-stage decision-making problems. Li *et al.* proposed a dynamic programming methods for solving the disassembly line design problem and testing the efficiency from the instance [22]. Zhou *et al.* applied the dynamic programming for representing the AND/OR graph of the disassembly sequences for improving the efficiency of disassembly process [23].

FP is another method for solving the optimization process of decision-making problems, which achieve the optimization conditions and extreme values of the objective function under the provision of easing conditions from fuzzification the bounds of constraints. Özceylan and

Paksoy applied FP for optimizing the DLBP joint with the reverse supply chain [24]. Kazancoglu and Ozturkoglu applied fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (FAHP) and fuzzy multi-objective optimization on the basis of ratio analysis (MOORA) for integrate considering the green and business perspective, minimizing the cycle time of the DLBP [25].

B. Heuristic algorithm

The heuristic method is based on empirical rules, which suitable for solving combinatorial optimization problems from past experience. The feasible solution cannot be determined as the optimal solution. Currently, the heuristic algorithms for remanufacturing DLBP are mainly based on the bionic algorithm, mainly including greedy algorithm, simulated annealing method, ant colony algorithm, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The classification of heuristic algorithm

Greedy algorithm and hill climbing algorithm are first proposed and compared into remanufacturing DLBP by McGovern and Gupta [26]. They proved both optimization algorithms can effectively solve large-scale DLBP for minimizing the workstations.

The essence of simulated annealing algorithm is an improved greedy algorithm. Through introducing random factors in the search process, the algorithm can avoid the result falling into the local optimum and realize the global optimum solution. Wang *et al.* proposed a multi-objective genetic simulated annealing algorithm for integrate considering the number of workstations, workload smoothness and disassemble profit, establishing the evaluation indicators and verifying the effectiveness of the algorithm [27]. Xia *et al.* proposed an adaptive simulated annealing genetic algorithm (ASAGA), for improving the global optimization ability of DLBP and compared this algorithm with genetic algorithm for proving the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm [28].

The basic principle of ant colony algorithm comes from the shortest path problem of ants foraging in nature. This algorithm suitable for searching the optimal solution of optimization problems. Mete and Çil proposed the ant colony algorithm for solving the assembly and disassembly lines hybrid system [29]. They subsequently proposed an interval search iterative ant colony optimization for shortening the cycle time of disassembly line and proved the better performance by compared to the random search, genetic algorithm and other versions of the algorithm [30].

C. Meta-heuristic algorithm

Meta-heuristic algorithm, also known as intelligent optimization algorithms of bionic swarms, is the improvement of heuristic algorithm, inspired from the foraging or evolution of biological groups in nature. The meta-heuristic algorithm is an algorithm based on experience and the combination of basic random algorithm and local search algorithm, which can obtain a feasible

solution to the problem within a specified time, but it cannot to determine the most optimal solution. The most common meta-heuristic algorithms applied in remanufacturing DLBP mainly including particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm, artificial bee colony (ABC) algorithm, genetic algorithm (GA), and tabu algorithm.

The PSO algorithm is an evolutionary computation technology, which originated from the study of bird predation behavior, and the optimal solution is found through collaboration and information sharing between individuals in the group. Kalayci and Gupta proposed the PSO algorithm and neighborhood-based mutation operator for optimizing the sequence-dependent DLBP, and proved the effectivity of this algorithm by compared to other related methods [31]. Xiao *et al.* proposed the adaptive hybrid PSO algorithm (AHPPO) and introduced the entropy for measuring the changing tendency of population diversity, the proposed algorithm is efficient to solve the higher complex DLBP compared with other evolutionary algorithms [32].

Figure 5. The classification of meta-heuristic algorithm

The ABC algorithm is other optimization method proposed by imitating the behavior of bees, which needs no special information from the research problem. Through the local optimization behavior of each individual artificial bees, the global optimal value is highlighted in the bee colony, with a faster convergence speed. Liu and Wang also presented an improved discrete ABC algorithm for solving the SDDLBP and evaluated the efficiency of the algorithm from comparing to other algorithms [33]. Gao *et al.* applied ABC algorithm for solving the DLBP considering the cost and working load for saving the energy consumption [34]. Cao *et al.* proposed a dual-population discrete ABC algorithm for comprehensively optimizing the multiple efficiency performance measures and validating by automotive engine disassembly line [35]. Wang *et al.* proposed a hybrid ABC algorithm with multi-stage evaluation method for solving the SDDLBP and proving the efficiency from compare to other meta-heuristic algorithms [36]. Wang *et al.* developed a discrete multi-objective ABC (MOABC) algorithm for end-of-life products disassembly, and certify the better performance through the example verification [37].

GA is a method of searching for the optimal solution by simulating the natural evolution process. When solving more complex combinatorial optimization problems, GA can get faster and better optimization results. Kalayci and Gupta proposed a hybrid method combines the GA with the variable neighborhood search method (VNSGA) for optimizing the SDDLBP [38]. Pistolesi *et al.* proposed the extremal multi-objective GA (EMOGA) for optimizing the multi-objective DLBP [39]. Ren *et al.* proposed the GA for solving the asynchronous parallel disassembly planning (aPDP), suitable for solving large-scale DLBP [40]. Liu *et*

al. proposed the GA for optimizing the multi-objective multi-robotic DLBP [41]. Mura *et. al.* proposed the GA for disassembly sequence considering the priority of the dangerous parts of the products [42]. Wang *et. al.* proposed an improved GA for optimizing the partial destructive DBLP and analyzing the performance by compared to other related algorithms [43]. Yuan *et. al.* proposed the ecological strategy NSGA-II for optimizing the multi-objective DLBP under the resource constraints condition [44]. Kucukkoc established the 2-GA for optimizing the two-sided DLBP (TDLBP) and gained better performance from the experimental results [45]. Meng and Zhang proposed the NSGA-II for improving and optimizing the multi-constraint remanufacturing DLBP [46].

Tabu algorithm starts from an initial feasible solution, selects a series of specific directions to search for the optimal solution, and prohibits repeating the previous directions, so as to achieve the global optimal solution. Kalayci and Gupta first applied the tabu algorithm into SDDLBP for optimizing the multi objectives and prove the efficiency of this algorithm [47]. Alshibli *et. al.* adopted the tabu search for improving the optimal solution and the disassembly sequencing model [48].

There are some other meta-heuristic algorithms applied for the remanufacturing disassembly process such as beam search algorithm [49], artificial fish swarm algorithm [50], firefly algorithm [51], flower pollination algorithm [52], fruit fly optimization algorithm [53].

III. THE COMPARE OF DLBP ALGORITHMS

From the reviewed literature, it can be found that researchers mainly conduct research from two directions, including establish the DLBP models and optimizing algorithms. The main methods applied in the remanufacturing disassembly process reviewed in the previous section have different advantages and disadvantages.

Although the exact algorithms can effectively find the most optimal solution to the problem, the speed of exact algorithm is slow. Meanwhile, due to the NP-hard characteristic of DLBP, with the increasing complexity of the disassembly target and the expanding of the problem scale, the solution space scale increases exponentially. Therefore, the exact algorithm cannot meet the requirement of solving the large-scale and high-complexity DLBP.

The heuristic algorithm mainly solves the optimization problems according to the formulated heuristic rules. The advantage of the algorithm is the solution speed is fast and the efficiency is also high. Apply the relative suitable solution algorithm to obtain the optimal solution. But because of the optimization DLBP with the NP-hard characteristics, this kind of algorithms are easily to obtain the local optimal solution, resulting in low accuracy. The heuristic algorithm is suitable for small-scale and rapid solutions, but not valid for large-scale and high complexity solutions. Simultaneously, it is unable to determine whether the heuristic algorithm obtains the global optimal solution, and the heuristic algorithms are not universal.

Meta-heuristic algorithm can be regarded as the improvement of heuristic algorithm. It is a combination of

global and local search, leading to the shorter optimizing time and higher quality. The disadvantage of meta-heuristic algorithm is the different search strategies need to be formulated for different DLBP, which leads to the higher model complexity. There are restrictions on the setting of model parameters, which are not suitable for solving large-scale DLBP as well.

TABLE II. COMPARE OF DISASSEMBLY LINE ALGORITHMS

Algorithm	Advantages	Disadvantages
Exact algorithm	Simple algorithm, Exact solution	Solving speed is slow, Unable to solve large-scale problems
Heuristic algorithm	Fast solution, High efficiency	Low solution accuracy, Not universal, Single function
Meta-Heuristic algorithm	High efficiency Fast solution Able to solve large-scale problems	High algorithm complexity Easily lead to local optimization

IV. THE FINDINGS FROM THE REVIEW

Briefly summary, most of the papers are mainly focus on developing the models and algorithms for the optimizing of remanufacturing DLBP. There are some findings and comments through the review of these papers:

- The traditional research on the remanufacturing disassembly line mainly focuses on disassembly sequence planning and disassembly line balancing problems, and most of the researched disassembly line balancing problem models are very similar.
- There are a great number of articles just employed single algorithm for optimizing DLBP, which achieving the single target optimization process. With the improvement of algorithms, some articles proposed some hybrid algorithms for solving the multi-objectives optimization of DLBP.
- Current proposed algorithms are mainly added random or fuzzy parameters to the constructed deterministic model for the optimization of remanufacturing DLBP. Among them, task processing time is one of the most commonly parameters as the uncertain factors, and there are other related uncertain factors considered in the DLBP, including: task failure, energy consumption, etc. Developing the dynamic programming of DLBP.
- Because of the DLBP characteristics of NP-hard, it is difficult to find the most optimized methods for multi-objective optimal solution. Currently, the most widely applied algorithms are heuristics, and these methods only focus on the certain specific scenario. Heuristic algorithms are also not universal and robust, leading the solution accuracy is not high.
- The proposed algorithms are mainly tested and verified by simulation experiments, and there is no algorithm suitable for large-scale DLBP (setting more than 30 related parameters). As the

complexity of the model increases, the efficiency and accuracy of the solution will decrease.

- The existing research on resource constrained disassembly line balance problem belongs to the combination of resource constrained scheduling problem and line balance problem. Few studies pay attention to the rescheduling and rebalancing issues when the system resources change due to a certain failure, that is, the robustness of the disassembly line system.

With the rapid increase numbers and categories as well as the disassembly complexity of the of disposal products, the existing models and algorithms have no ability for solving the large-scale, multi-optimization goals, dynamic and efficient remanufacturing disassembly process.

V. FUTURE RESEARCH CHALLENGES

According to the summary and review of the optimization algorithms for solving remanufacturing DLBP. There are some research challenges on the DLBP:

- Construct the algorithm suitable for automated remanufacturing disassembly line system, with the increased number and diversity of disassembly products.
- Design and develop the improved algorithms, hybrid algorithms, swarm and evolutionary algorithm for solving large-scale DLBP.
- Develop the new applicable algorithms for considering the comprehensive influence of multiple objectives and factors of DLBP, including the number of workstations, cycle time, cost control, profit and energy consumption, etc.
- Construct the novel comprehensive algorithm for integrating study the disassembly line, reverse supply chain, product inspection and other remanufacturing processes.

Nowadays, although the dramatically development of the artificial intelligence algorithms, the application of smart and novel heuristic algorithms into DLBP of smart remanufacturing do not get much attention. As one of the pretty novel application field of the smart algorithm, with the continuous development of smart remanufacturing, the development of improved and hybrid algorithms for better efficiency and performance for the multi-objective DLBP can not only achieving the fully automation and multi-optimization targets of the DLBP, but also saving the total cost of smart remanufacturing process.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper mainly reviewed three main categories of multiple objective optimization algorithms for solving remanufacturing DLBP. Through the review, indicating as the current better optimization algorithm, the meta-heuristic algorithms still have the limitation, which not suitable for large-scale, multi-type products and objectives. Moreover, all the optimization algorithms cannot ensure getting the global optimum results. Therefore, put some future research challenges and direction of the construction and improvement of optimization algorithms for

remanufacturing DLBP. With the development and improvement of multiple optimization algorithms, the remanufacturing disassembly line can handle multi objectives, more complex tasks, achieving the improvement of process efficiency as well.

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